

Dance + Ball games = True!

An innovative lesson design

Introduction

Introduction and Background

Why?

- Student's perspective: Participate in games and movement activities. Develop general movement abilities. Develop participation, involvement, and learning!
- Main learning outcome: The student performs movement activities involving complex movements in different contexts and adapts their movements to the purpose of the activity.*
- Teacher's Perspective: Opportunity for professional development by trying new lesson designs and exchanging experiences with other active teachers.

What?

- BRESS** with Dance and Ball play

How?

Progression using dance and ball play, and with BRESS and games in small groups as tools for developing participation, involvement, and social skills. 6 lessons over 6 weeks. One suggestion can be to repeat every lesson. If you for example have two lessons per week with the students that is a preferable plan since the students then have a chance to develop even more. Concerning the professional development as a teacher we recommend that you reflect after each lesson and that you engage conversations with your colleagues (see suggestions of reflective questions further down)

*This is taken from the Swedish curriculum for secondary school (Skolverket, 2022)

**BRESS – Body, Relation, Effort, Shape, Space, a movement-theoretical framework inspired by and based on Rudolf Laban's movement theories, e.g. LMA – Laban Movement Analyses (Frisk & Svanström, 2023). See separate presentation

Introduction

General Appearance of the Lessons:

During the lessons, each lesson will be characterized by a part of BRESS. The game is based on a game-based approach, eg. TGfU (Bunker & Thorpe, 1986), which means that we start and end with a holistic perspective. Thus, we adhere to two theoretical frameworks/models.

The lessons follow three content tracks:

- Movement and Dance (to music)
- Integration of dance and ball play
- Ball games

Within these three tracks, there is progression and the possibility for immersion, but the three tracks also run parallel, which means that the entire lesson design also follows a progression where students are given the opportunity to develop different abilities. Among other things, through:

- Games in small teams and with principles for basic play! Here, different game forms are tested in small team formats and with different types of pedagogical rules.
- Exercises with and without a ball (with music) based on the needs of the individual and group for development and learning in the game.

As a support to you some of the parts of the design are exemplified with short videos of dances, exercises and games.

Lesson design - overview

Lesson 1: The "whole"

The dance is made to easily reach the "product."

The "game" is designed for participation regardless of the individual's different conditions and prior knowledge. We suggest using the following music: [Spotify playlist](#)

Lessons 2-5: Exercises based on BRESS game development with movements to music and exercises with a ball

- Lesson 2 emphasis on Body
- Lesson 3 emphasis on Shape and Space
- Lesson 4 emphasis on Effort
- Lesson 5 emphasis on Relations

Lesson 6: The "whole"

Dance an advanced version of the dance (with a ball) and play the game

Questions to reflect upon after (each) lesson in the design.

- What was the content of the planned lesson?
- What was the learning objective for the lesson?
- Briefly describe how well the content corresponded with the learning objective (aim) of the lesson.
- Was the learning objective achieved and if what contributed to that?
- Identify (give examples of) some specific moments, strategies, events that relate to the lesson design.
- In what ways did I find the implementation of the lesson design useful and/or challenging?
- What signals of learning (responses) did I perceive from the students that I can link to the purpose of the lesson design?
- What purposes do I perceive my implementation of the lesson design has served for my students?
- Did I make any choices that differ from the original planning of the lesson design? If so, which ones and why?
- How might insights from using the lesson design in this lesson inform or change how I approach subsequent lessons?

Questions to reflect on during the collegial dialogue.

- I have experienced this as an opportunity from working on the lesson design.
- What have I experienced as challenging?
- Please give examples of some specific moments, strategies, events directly related to the implementation of the lesson design.
- Give examples of some specific moments, strategies, events that concern the eventual learning of the students.
- Give examples of some specific moments, strategies, events that concern your learning.
- Give examples of some specific moments, strategies, events that concern the students learning.
- Experience of working from a digital material.
- Experience of working with different movement practices integrated with each other.

BRESS-concept – A movement theoretical framework

Langton (2007); Ravn (2001); Frisk & Svanström (2023)

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WHY the BRESS – concept?

Langton:

- Helps student to see the wholeness of bodily movement
- The framework provides the opportunity for understanding of:
 - The language of the body
 - The body and its possibilities of movement
 - Strategy, tactics and patterns
 - Cognitive knowledge not just practical skills

Ravn:

- A tool for exploring/experimenting with and talking about movement
- BRESS – A starting point for a movement language
- A language about movement (and experience of) without value; only description of

Engdahl et al.

- Simple, recognizable and descriptive terms

The BRESS – concept

- **Body**
- The body's possibilities to move
- Where is the movement initiated?
- Total or isolated movements
- Functions: Bending – Stretching – Twisting
- Connections: "Head – Tail", Right/Left side, Diagonals etc
- **Relations**
- Relation to/with:
 - Ones own body
 - Other bodies
 - The room
 - The music
 - Rhythm
 - Artefacts

The BRESS – concept

Effort – Dynamic expression

- Execution in relation to composition
- The awareness of the student
- How!

The BRESS – concept

Shape – Form

- Stick/pin (straight)
- Wall (big)
- Ball (round/small)
- Spiral

Shape – Trace (What trace does the movement leave on the floor?)

- Line
- Curve
- Circle
- Spiral

The BRESS – concept

▪ Space – Room

- The personal room
- The general room
- Levels (low/deep, middle, high)
- Fronts/directions – compass (eg. Forward, backwards, left/right)
- Zones (kinesphere) – Near reach, Mid reach, Far reach
- Planes – Sagital (wheel), Frontal (door), Horizontal (table)

The BRESS – concept

References

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Movement and dance + ball games = True!

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Lesson 1

Lesson 1 – "The whole"

Purpose: In this first lesson, we focus on the entirety of both dance and games. The inspiration comes from TGfU (GBA), but we could also say that it is about seeing the difference between "learning to dance versus learning a dance" (Lundvall & Meckbach 2007) or if we translate that into the world of ballgame: "learning to play versus learning a game" . Admittedly, the whole includes performing a dance and a game, but the focus is on developing (discovering) the ability to dance and play.

BRESS Concepts: In this first lesson, where the whole is based on a game-based learning approach (Game Based Approach/Teaching Games for Understanding), we do not focus much on the BRESS concepts, but it might be a good idea to introduce the various components to prepare the students for the upcoming lessons.

Didactic Considerations: Regarding the dance parts, choose either to work with the dance snake leading to funk dance or the small dance phrase that can be developed according to the suggestions provided in the material. In the game, work with shorter periods of play and allow for reflection within the "team" on how they can change their offensive/defensive play.

Lesson 1 – Movement and dance

- **Three variations of Dances**
- **Dance Snakes**
- **Music:** "Can't Stop the Feeling" - Justin Timberlake (leading into the funk dance)
 - Students follow each other in a line (hands on shoulders in a normal world)
 - Walk 7 steps forward, bring feet together in a small jump (on 8)
 - Three steps to the side, jump together (on 4) where every other student goes right and every other goes left, then back to the line in three steps, jump together.
 - Repeat from the beginning
 - A variation can be to turn 180 degrees in the jump back to the line so that the whole dance snake changes front.

Dance Snake

- **"The Funk Dance"**
- **Music:** Some mainstream hip-hop, funky song.

The dance is based on the same principles as the dance snakes above but is somewhat developed. Formation – in pairs in a circle against the dance direction (counterclockwise)

- Walk in the dance direction 7 steps forward, bring feet together in a small jump (on 8)
- See above side steps (original dance above) but with the difference that you finish with a jump and a 90° turn towards your dance partner
- Standing facing each other. Cross arms over the chest (1), extend arms to the side (2) repeat (3-4). Clap in front of the body (1), clap behind the body (2), pause (3), clap double high five so that the pair's right hands meet "double high five" (4).
- Keep the high handhold and walk 8 "funky" steps together clockwise around to the starting position, to start the dance again from turn 1.

Funk Dance

Lesson 1 – Movement and Dance

- **"The small Dance Phrase" –**
- **Music:** any upbeat 4/4 song (preferably with an even structure, i.e., 8 bars/theme)
 - 1-8 Walk forward
 - 1-4 Side step to the right 1-4 Side step to the left
 - 1-8 Walk backward
 - 1-8 Make a circle around yourself

The "small" dance phrase

Developments:

- In a group, change/add:
 - Arms
 - Time
 - Arms
 - Body

Didactic Reflection:

Choose to either work with dances 1 and 2 or dance 3 in your progression. If the funk dance (no. 2) is your goal, we suggest starting with the dance snakes to "embed" the basic steps. If you conduct 2 lessons on the same theme, one idea could be to do the dance snakes in lesson 1a and the funk dance in lesson 1b (with a short repetition beforehand). If you choose "The Little Dance Phrase," lesson 1b can be developed through the suggested changes above.

Lesson 1 – Ballgame

- **The game - Wiball**

Small sided games for example 4 versus 4

Travelling rules like in basketball, rotation allowed

Foul rule as in basketball on your own half of the court

Wi-ball

- **Didactic reflection**

The film above shows the game in its basic form. One idea could be to play shorter periods and let the separate teams reflect on what they need to do in order to score "goals".

WIBOLL

Figure : The principles of the game showed in the figure. To observe is the different kind of difficulties the players have to handle on the defensive and the offensive halves of the court. The defensive side could be called the "controlling" side and the offensiv half of the court could be called the "risky side"

WIBOLL Rules

The game is an invasion game with a lot of ingredients of basketball but also with the playform tagging players in the game.

- There are two ways to score in the game: One way is to pass the ball to a teammate on the "passing goal area" (could be defined by a gymnastic carpet). The other way to make a goal is to dribble the ball in to an area, for example the three second area of the basketball court. The rules for the offensive team to dribble and pass the ball is taken from the rules in basketball.
- The player with the ball is allowed to move in all directions when he/she is dribbling the ball but it's not allowed to run/move with the ball without dribbling it.
- Steprules like in basketball also with the rules of rotation.
- On the defensive half of the court the players have the right to hold the ball and the opponents do not have the right to take the ball out of the hands of the ballholder. The opponents can only take the ball by stealing a pass or by stealing the ball when it's been dribbled. Fouling rules like in basketball on the defensive half of the court. The defensive part of the court is made to make it easier for the players and to make it possible to build up a controlled way to play the ball by the players in the team.
- On the offensive half of the court there is different kind of rules. The ballholder loses the ball being tagged by a defensive player and has as soon being tagged to drop the ball to the floor. The ball is picked up by a player in the defensive team and is by that in play again. Conclusion: An offensive player with the ball have to pass the ball before being tagged. The offensive part of the court is the risky and more challenging area in the game.
- The ball cannot be passed directly from defensive half to a goalzone. The ball has to pass the half court line with dribbling or passing to a player on the offensive side with the risk being tagged before a goal can be scored.
- Roles in the game: The game give the players possibilities depending on how used they are to ballgames. Depending on their knowledge of ballgames they can act in the game differently. In an easier way in the controlling area on the defensive half or risky on the offensive half of the court.

Lesson 1 – "The whole"

Reflection

Suggested questions(for the students):

- How did you experience the dance?
- How did you experience the game?
- Is there anything special in either that you noticed?
- Was there anything that was challenging in your experiences?

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Lesson 2

Lesson 2 – Body, "Take the ball"

Aim: In this lesson, the idea is to start working on the different parts that were presented and worked on during the "whole". The idea is to enable the development of movement skills both in the own body and together with music and ball. That the students are invited into an inclusive environment where they have the opportunity to familiarise themselves with the different parts in a safe way.

BRESS-concepts: Within the concept of body, the focus is on creating awareness of which part of the body is moving, where the movement starts and where it continues. How much of the body is involved, i.e. is it total movements or more isolated movements that are performed. Even the basic prerequisites for movement 'bending, stretching, twisting' are within this concept.

The ball: In terms of guiding the ball game, this lesson gives students the opportunity to develop their ball skills by working with the ball themselves but also in relation to others.

Didactical considerations: Adaptation to the group is crucial. You know the students and make the choices you need based on the maturity of the group and what exercises may suit them. Preferably try to get started as quickly as possible with the various exercises to keep a flow in the lesson. This usually gives them the opportunity not to start thinking and hesitating about their participation.

Lesson 2 – Movement and Dance

- **Balloon exercise**
- **Music:** Deep focus or another soft calm music
 - All gets a balloon and the task is to keep it in the air, in motion without using hands or feet
 - Explore the room
 - Explore being down on the floor
 - Try only to have contact with the balloon with the backside of the body
 - 2 by 2 (one balloon per couple)
 - Pass the balloon between each other (still no hand and feet)
 - Here you can enhance the notion of where the movement starts by calling out with which bodypart you are using
- **Robots and Slime**
- **Music:** A music with a mixed between staccato and legato (file linked)
 - A tag game where the Slime (the tagger) are to transform (by tagging) all of the robots to slime.
 - The slime(s) (😊) can only move to the "slime music"
 - The robots can only move to the "robot music"
 - A variation could be that it is the robot that are the tagger instead (usually this variant is much faster to implement, why?)
- **Robots and Slime alternative**
 - A more strength/physical variation of the game could be for students to walk on all fours (hands and feet, stomach eith up or down) where it is possible to vary who are the tagger. For example stomach down taggers.
 - (With the younger ones, one can find animals or other metaphors that are the two antagonists.)

Lesson 2 – Integration with ball

- **Keep a soft ball in motion** (the same exercise as with balloon but with a soft ball instead)
 - Everyone has a soft ball
 - Keep the ball in the air (Start by trying without using hand and feet)fötter)
 - Pass the ball between eachother in pairs (Try without using hands and feet)
- **Robots- and Slimeball**
 - The game is performed in the same way as above but all students have a (soft) ball
 - The different characters (robots and slime) and the music give freedom/inspiration to how the ball is used BUT it has to be in motion (bouncing, in the air etc) and with an attempt to relate to the music.
 - The actual throwing of the ball is done by the thrower touching the person being thrown with the ball (not throwing)

Lesson 2 – Ballplay

Before we start:

"What did one need in the game (from lesson 1) to succeed? (Discuss for a minute with the friend closest by)"

Basic technical skills

- To be able to bounce the ball on the spot and moving around
 - To be able to pass and to receive the ball
 - Being able to stop with the ball
 - Being able to rotate
 - Practised for example as below
- **Passing circle**
 - Half of the group in a large circle. Half of the group inside the circle.
 - The balls can either start from those inside or those in the circle.
 - The participants inside the circle move and receive the ball from those in the circle, pass the ball back and move to receive another pass from someone else in the circle.
 - A variant is that during the pass, the roles of the person inside the circle and the person outside the circle change.
 - Progression: Passing circle with one or more people tagging those with the ball in the circle, free by passing those in the circle and then also changing places with them, testing the level of difficulty by testing the number of balls and rolling

Passing Circle

Lesson 2 – Ballplay

- **Discussion: (In pairs or in a whole group)**

"How do you pass?" "How is the passing technique?" Demonstrate and practise as below.

"How did you move with the ball?", "Could you run with the ball?"

- **Passing technique**

- In pairs: Try one-handed and two-handed passes, rotating and receiving passes, bouncing the ball - stopping and passing to a mate

- **Who wants to be a football pro???**

- One student who stands in the middle, asks the group standing by the side of the gym "who wants to be a football pro?", everyone shouts 'I do', the centre person shouts 'show me then' and the group shows by dribbling the ball from short side to short side without getting tagged. If you get tagged, you also stay in the middle. Gradually the number of taggers will increase and it will be harder to cross the room.

- **Game exercise 4 against 1**

- The team have to do 5 passes without losing the ball, practise passing in the quiet zone (own half)
- 4 attackers 1 defender. 5 passes to succeed
- "How do you pass the ball past the defender?"

- **Game exercise 4 against 4 with two "jokers"**

- Five passes without losing the ball (jokers always belong to the team holding the ball)
- Game 3 against 3 with two players who always belong to the team with the ball. Means that in practice the team with the ball is always 5 attackers against 3 defenders.
- "When should you pass and when should you bounce the ball to succeed in the passing game?"

Wi-ball with jokers

Discussion between the players about possible options to successfully solve the situations and questions asked by the teacher should be included in the exercises

Reflection

Suggested questions:

- When you 'played' with the balloon, which body parts did you use the most?
- When you modelled the slime and the robot, how did you experience the body? Any difference between the two?
- How did you experience the passing circle?
- How did you experience the game with jokers? How did the team discuss about tactics?

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Lesson 3

Lesson 3 – Shape och Space, Being playable

Aim: In this lesson we explore shape and space in different ways. Booth shape of the body and traces on the floor/in space and becoming aware of other people in the room.

BRESS-concepts: Although the plastic form of the body is also included, it is perhaps above all the traces in space formed by both how we travel and what traces movements (with or without artefacts) leave behind that are in focus. The spatial becomes a central part in that the students relate to both themselves and the space (both the personal and the general) eventually also together with an artefact (the ball) to later need to increase their awareness about others in the room.

To be playable: Creating awareness of where I am as a player in relation to my fellow players and opponents is a prerequisite for being playable. Here we practice clarifying this role.

Didactical conciderations: One of the exercises in this lesson is "swarming", i.e. walking around the room in a jumble. Here there is a "risk" that the students will walk more in clusters and stick to the walls. Therefore, it is positive if you as a teacher are involved in the exercise as a catalyst. It may also be an idea to make the room smaller if you have a large room available. There are quite a few exercises presented, here it is important to make choices based on the group and what has been done before.

Lesson 3 – Movement and Dance

➤ **Mirroring tag-game with a twist**

- **Musik:** "Can't stop the feeling" - Justin Timberlake or another uptempo song. Can also be beneficial to vary between genres and tempo.

A starting point here is that by setting pedagogical rules, we transform the tag game from a 'wild game' to a more controlled one where the music controls speed and perhaps even movement patterns.

- One or more cobblers
- If large hall, limit the surface
- Students may only move in relation to the basic pulse (interpretable as the double pulse can be compared to running) so a clarification can be that they work (walk) in the basic pulse (which can certainly then be increased in tempo and come close to running)
- If one gets tagged, the student takes a statue/position/form
- To become free, a friend should assume the same shape/position/form opposite or next to.
- Variation could be that instead of the student taking a static position, they make a movement to be imitated to get free.
- A further option is for the tagger to give the tagged student a shape or movement
- Change the tagger often

Lesson 3 – Movement and Dance

- **Swarming**

- **Music:** "Chicane" – Offshore

The basic idea of swarming is to walk around the room in a "jumble". If it's a large sports hall, it's a good idea to limit the surface area to create more movement in the room.

- Have eyecontact
- Empty spaces (eg. Walkto spaces that become empty)
- Different kinds of meetings/interactions
- Mirroring
- Jump/roll/rotate together
- Walk in straight/curved paths
- Be far away/close/and in between eachother
- Slow motion (using the whole body and also try to be on the floor)

Swarming

Lesson 3 – Integrating ball/ballplay

- **Swarming with ball**
- **Music:** "Panjabi Beats" - Dimitri from London or another instrumental song with a clear pulse.
 - Basically, you can work with the same exercises as without the ball
 - Let the students be free how to use the ball from start (they can toss it in the air or bounce for example)
 - Let the students bounce as they want in relation to the music (later on you can guide them towards being in pulse)
 - Challenge/mirror each other

Swarming with ball

Lesson 3 – Ballgame

- **Where's my mate?**

"What is important to keep track of your friends in the exercise?"

- The group participants walk around the room.
- Keep a distance of 1-2 meters (small room) to all other participants. Adjust your movement if someone comes too close to you.
- When an empty space opens up, participants take the chance to quickly conquer that spot with a sprint step.
- Make eye contact with someone in the group. When making eye contact, the two participants freeze their movement for a few moments before moving on.
- As above but at eye contact do as in the 'mirror', one (who decides spontaneously by the participants) of the two initiates a movement and the other mimics as able. The 'mimic' decides when the movement should be cancelled to move on and find a new partner.
- As above but on eye contact, a ball change is made. Both release their ball with a powerful bounce and sprint to their mate's ball.
- Divide the group into two groups. Half stand still, the other half dribble the ball freely. Suddenly one of the dribblers stops with the ball. Then all the dribblers should stop with the ball and the stationary ones should start bouncing. This is done alternately.
- Can be done so that everyone dribbles at the same time, one stops which makes everyone stop, one starts dribbling which makes everyone start dribbling. It can be done even more easily so that the leader signals the start and stop.

Lesson 3– Ballplay

- **Pass the ball**

In pairs, one ball per pair

- As the previous exercise where those without the ball move and those with the ball are still. When one of those without the ball stops, all participants without the ball should stop and those with the ball should start bouncing.
- Pass the ball in pairs
- Pass the ball in pairs while everyone is moving in a jumble. Keep the distance, be playable.
- Make the exercise progressively more difficult. Move behind a bunch of other participants in the passing shadow and dive into a ‘gap’ to receive a pass. The ball holder, meanwhile, is allowed to bounce the ball to find the right passing angle.
- Players without the ball act as ‘above ball players’ hiding behind one of the other group participants (hide and seek). Players with the ball act as ‘van ball players’, dribbling the ball to a good passing angle and passing the ball to the hiding player.

Lesson 3– Ballplay

- **"The monkey" in the middle**

In groups with one ball per group. One person in the middle

- Groups of at least four pupils per group with one ball per group. One pupil is in the centre of the group and the others have to pass the ball without the centre person getting hold of the ball. If the centre person gets hold of the ball, change the person in the middle. Change the centre person after, for example, 7 passes if the centre person has not caught the ball. Then "the group has been very good at passing the ball".
- One ball per group.
- Increasing the level of difficulty: Tagging the ball holder gives conquest of the ball.
- This exercise can also be done "one on one" or "two on one" to show the possibilities that open up when you are not alone, i.e. there is someone to pass to (see film clip)

Game exercise

WI-BOLL with Jokers

- The game three against three with two "jokers", (jokers are players who are extra players in the attacking team. When the defenders win the ball, the jokers also change teams and belong to the team that has the ball). In this case, it means that the team with the ball is five players including the jokers.

Wi-ball with jokers

Lesson 3

Reflection

Suggested questions:

- Was there any difference walking in straight versus curved paths? Any difference when you had a ball?
- How did it feel to work in slow motion?
- How did you relate the bouncing to the music when you were swarming?
- In the game, how did you make yourself playable?

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Lesson 4

Lesson 4 – Effort / How

Aim: In this lesson, the idea is to raise awareness of the "how", i.e. different parameters that affect how the movement/exercise/game is done. In previous lessons, the "what" and "where" have been central parts and now we play around the "how" instead.

BRESS - concepts: In Effort, the concept is divided into four factors that then affect how the movement/exercise is performed and experienced: Time (sudden - sustained), Force/Resistance (very/heavy - small/light), Space (direct - flexible) and Flow (free - bound). If one factor changes, other factors will be affected and awareness of this can create development opportunities both in the dance, work with the ball and in the game.

Didactical considerations: There are many exercises to choose from in this lesson too. Make choices based on the group and your progress. In the various dance-related exercises and the pulse exercise with a ball, it can be an advantage for you as a teacher to be involved as a catalyst.

Lesson 4 – Movement and Dance

- **Freestyler**

- **Musik: Freestyler "Boomfunk MC"**

- One or more "tagger" with a remote control
- The group moves around in the room as they want (or give them different tasks)
- The "tagger" controls the rest of the group by "zapping the individuals to:
 - Freeze
 - Play - Continue
 - Fastforward
 - Slow motion
 - Rewind
- Always play in between the other tasks to "set them free"
- Start with each commando separately (change tagger with commando)
- Then when the students have tried all commandos (efforts) mix it up. The tagger is in control.

Lesson 4 – Intergration with ball

- **Pulse exercise with ball**
- **Music:** A song with a clear beat for example "Nighttrain" - Pearlcode

Let the students choose a ball (bouncy) that they are comfortable with

One by one

- Go around and bounce the ball (freely)
- Guide them to find the different pulsebeats (1, 2, 3, 4 if 4/4 measurement)
- Guide them to bounce in the basic pulse (bpm around 80-100)
- With right/left hand, both
- Bounce in halfpulse (2, 4 or 1, 3)
- Try to walk in halfpulse and bounce in basic pulse and the other way around
- Try to walk/run in doublepulse and bounce in half or basic pulse
- Other rhythms (for ex 2, And 4)

Two by two (or three if uneven)

- Pass the ball between each other in the music (start of on one beat for ex 1, but change along the way)
- Bouncepass
- On halfpulse (1, 3 or 2, 4)
- Standing still opposite each other, next to each other, moving around
- Try to deliver the ball on different beats in the music
- Try different passes (high, low, rolling, fast, slow)

Pass the ball in the pulse of the music

Lesson 4– Ballgame

- **Numerical advantage** - *“When to pass in order to keep the ball from the defenders?”*
 - 6 against 2 or similar group size.
 - The group of six must make a certain number of passes, e.g. 10, to win.
 - The group of two should make significantly fewer passes, e.g. 3, in the team to win.
 - Can be done by making it sufficient for the defenders to touch the opponents' ball to obtain it or by having to interrupt the opponents' pass to win the ball.
 - Increase in difficulty: tagging the ball holder results in the conquest of the ball.
- **Keeping the ball within the team**
 - Two teams for ex. 4 by 4. One ball
 - The ballholding team should pass the ball within the team in order to keep the other team from conquering the ball.
 - Conquered ball means that the other team starts passing the ball.
 - How many passes can the team achieve before losing the ball?
 - No taking the ball from each other's hands only breaking the passes and interfering.
 - No walking with the ball only when bouncing
 - Variation (to challenge):
 - The challenger can conquer the ball in the actual bounce.
 - Several balls
 - *Short games with tactical discussions in the breaks*

- **The game – Wi-ball**

“Tactical discussions: How’s the game functioning now in comparison to the first time?”

“What do we need to practice more in order to develop within the game?”

Lesson 4 - Reflection

Reflection

Suggested questions:

- Describe the difference between working fast, slow, standing still.
- Was there a difference when you had to bounce at a certain pulse beat and when the ball had to be delivered at a certain pulse beat?
- What was it like to move around the room and keep an eye on your partner while keeping up with the music?
- What did you realise from the numerical advantage?

Dance + Ballgames = True!

An innovative lesson design

Lesson 5

Lesson 5 - Relations

Aim: In this lesson, the idea is to give students the opportunity to practice even more consciously the relational perspective, although this is always present. Here we work with exercises in which the relationship to oneself, one's peers, the room, the music and the ball are in focus.

BRESS-concept: Even if the different relational perspectives are intertwined, it can be good to stop and think about what kind of relationship is in focus right now: Is it to the music i.e. to be able to bounce in the basic pulse or is it to "find" the mates in the playing field? By trying to separate them, we can increase awareness of how they affect us and how they interact.

Didactical considerations: Several exercises are presented here with many different relational perspectives, make choices according to the group and what has been achieved. It can be helpful if you as a teacher are involved as a catalyst in the different exercises. In the various games, work with shorter periods and let the students reflect on how they can strengthen their relationships in order to "succeed" with the task.

Lesson 5 – Movement and Dance

- **Swarming** – development from previous time
- **Music:** "Crazy Benny" – Safri Duo; "Winter's song" – Bob Moses; "Walking with elephants" – Ten Walls
 - Walkin the pulse of the music
 - Go to places that becomes empty
 - One stops everybody stops – (*possibly without music*)
 - Everyone in the grop can stop the movement in the whole group by stopping: When all is in stillness anyone can start the movement again by continue to walk.
 - Try with a higher tempo and also by running
 - The triangle (*preferable without music*)
 - Everyone decides to relate to two persons in the group (in secret)
 - When the game starts all should place themselves in the relation of a triangle to the two individuals.
 - Since (most likely) everyone has chosen differently the game will continue "forever".
- **Shoulder by shoulder**
- **Music:** "Deep focus" or any othe soft and calm music (although one can play with different tempos and genres)
 - 2 by 2 (or 3 by 3) with a balloon or a soft ball between:
 - Shoulders
 - The couple (or trio) walks around without dropping the ball
 - One is leading (the other one with eyes shut)
 - Change
 - Both leads and follows (both eyes open)
 - Challenge them to wak in curved paths, straight paths, move in different levels
 - Also try with the ball between other bodyparts (hips, backs, head)
 - Now do the same excersise (from the start) without the ball.
 - Reflect about the difference of leading/following with or without the ball

Lesson 5 – Intergration with ball

- **Repeat bounce in pulse**

- Close to each other
- Far away from each other
- Somewhere in between

- **Numberball**

- A group of 3 or 4
- Bouncepass the ball (1 to 2 to 3 to 4 to 1)
- First standing still just to establish the pattern
- No pass the ball on a certain pulsebeat (for ex 1 or 4)
- First standing still then moving around in the room.
- Now the ball should be delivered on a certain pulsebeat to the next partner
- Variations (more complex patterns) but still in the music
 - Try different kind of passes (high, rolling quick)
 - Random order within the group (pass the one that is playable)
 - Really move around the room and interact with the other groups but keep the passing the ball within the group.

Numberball

Lesson 5– Bollgame

- **Numerical advantage (being down one player)**
 - Two-team games on a regular/smaller surface in groups of 10, the game is played 4 against 4 but with some pedagogical rules:
 - some players are not allowed to defend in either the offensive or defensive half of the pitch
 - only one/two/three players may go down to their own half of the pitch and defend there
 - Short matches and time outs with tactical discussions in the groups
- **Small team games**
 - Games with fewer participants and a smaller field.
 - Score a goal with a pass in the offensive half of the pitch
 - Pedagogical rules e.g. in 5 vers 5 games
 - Short game rounds with tactics talk in between
- **The game – Wiball**
 - Maybe try to add the thought of being in numerical advantage/disadvantage.
 - ”What tactical aspect do the team have to consider?”

Lesson 5 - Relations

Reflection

Suggested question:

- What was it like to relate to two mates as a triangle?
- In the game, are there any triangles?
- Was there anything that became clear when you had to hold a balloon between different body parts?
- What tactical aspects was discussed when the team is in numerical advantage/disadvantage?

Dance + Ball games = True!

An innovative lesson design

Lesson 6

Lesson 6 – The ”Whole”

Purpose: Now it's time to “tie the knot” and we ask ourselves if the lesson design has given the opportunity for students to: *Participate in games and play. Develop participation, involvement and learning!* By returning to the start, the purpose is partly for the students to be familiar with the material and in that be given the opportunity to see and experience their own development and partly for us teachers to see the students' development.

BRESS-concepts: In this lesson, none of the concepts are particularly in focus, but rather that the students show (bodily) understanding of the whole framework and that we teachers can see and verbalise what is happening.

Didactical conciderations: Depending on the choices you made for the dances in the first lesson, we suggest you to continue on that path but increase the complexity by adding the ball. There are suggestions for different approaches to the different dances without the ball first if you want to see how the pupils themselves can be given the opportunity to develop the foundations. During the game, give the students the opportunity to reflect on the various elements that have been in the spotlight during the series, such as playability and that they themselves can come up with the ‘answers’.

Lesson 6 – Movement and Dance

Repetitions of the dances

- **Dancesnakes**
- **Music:** "Can't stop the feeling" – Justin Timberlake; "I don't feel like dancing" – Maroon 5
 - Repeat the original dance
 - Add the "jumpturns"
 - Maybe change music (something with a clear character)
 - Let the students create own changes
- **The funkdance with a twis**
 - Repeat the original
 - Change music to something folkloristic (just let the students try without talking to much)
 - What happened? Why?
 - Any movement that doesnt feel "right" in the new musik?
 - Let the couples create variations to suit the new music
 - Maybe let two couple show each other and learn one anothers
- **The small dancephrase**
 - Repeat the dance/phrase
 - If (in the first lesson) the students didnt get to change/create themselves now is a good oportunity
 - Change music to another genre

Lesson 6 – Intergration with ball

- **Dancesnakes with ball**
- **Music:** A slower "heavier" music. Panjabi beats for example
 - All students gets a ball (a bouncy one)
 - In the steps forward bounce in different tempos or accents (2, 4, 6 for ex) catch the ball on 8 and jump together
 - In the sidesteps the jump can be replaced with a bounce instead
 - Let the students creat their own way of relating to the ball/the rhythm

Dance Snake with ball

- **The small phrase with ball**
 - Start in the original dance
 - In the steps forward, bounce in halfbeat
 - In the sidesteps bounce the ball on every beat
 - In the steps backwards, bounce in halfbeat
 - In the steps around oneself, do something individual with the ball
 - Let the students create dfferent rhythms, transitions, relations

The "Small" Dancephrase with ball

Lesson 6 – Intergration with ball

- **The funkdance with ball**

- All students have a ball but are still paired in two
- In the steps forward bounce in halfbeat (1,3,5,7 or 2,4,6,8)
- Either hold the ball while doing the sidesteps or find a relationship to the pulse
- When facing eachother bounce on everyother beat (so not bouncing in the same time)
- When going around it the students create their own way of relating to eachother with:
 - Bouncing
 - Ball to Ball contact
 - Combinations
- An alternative can be that the couple are sharing a ball and bouncing/throwing/passing it between eachother
- There are endless combinations 😊

Funk Dance with ball

Funk Dance with ball - variation

Lesson 6– Ballgame

- **Game: Wi-ball**
 - If time – choose some of the exercises from lesson 2-5 to start with
 - In short matches with tactical reflections in between.
- Wi-ball

Lesson 6 – The ”Whole”

Reflection

Reflection:

- How did you experience the dances now? Any difference from the first time, if describe!
- How did you experience dancing with a ball? Challenges?
- Did your role in the game change from the first lesson? What was different? Why?